

Thermal conductivity of composites

B. Schulz

Institut für Material- und Festkörperforschung
Kernforschungszentrum Karlsruhe

1) Introduction

When we define composites as two-or multiphase materials fabricated with the aim to combine the desirable properties of the phases to a more effective use in practice, then it is necessary to have a sufficient knowledge about the dependence of properties on new parameters, introduced by the combination of two-or more phases. The thermal conductivity belongs to a group of physical properties, which are defined by constitutive equations of the type

$$(1) \quad \vec{q} = -\lambda \text{grad } \bar{T}$$

other properties being the electrical conductivity, the dielectric constant and the magnetic permittivity. In what follows, these properties are called "conductivity (λ)". From equation (1) it is obvious, that such properties will not obey in general the rule of mixtures, i.e. the resulting conductivity of a mixture of two phases will not depend on the conductivity of the pure phases and their concentration alone.

Theoretical considerations in the continuum theory, its application to the conductivity of two phase materials /1,2/, as well as

physical experiments have shown: The amount of particles n per volume, their shape F and orientation to the direction of (for example) an homogeneous electrostatic field give rise to a perturbation of the original field, which results in a general function.

$$(2) \quad \lambda = f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, c_v, F, \text{Orientation}); c_{v1} + c_{v2} = 1$$

λ - resulting conductivity of the composite, $\lambda_{1,2}$ - conductivity of the pure phases 1,2 c_v - volume concentration; which is related to the amount of particles per volume n and their size by

$$(3) \quad c_v = n \cdot \bar{V}$$

\bar{V} , being the mean volume of a single particle. The three parameters volume concentration, shape and orientation, called stereometric parameters, decide by their distribution in volume, whether the composite is heterogeneous or quasihomogeneous. Fig.(1) shows three examples of heterogeneous composite arising by an abrupt change of the concentration, of the shape and of the orientation of the phases, whereas fig. 2 shows an example for a quasihomogeneous composite. From this it follows: a composite is quasihomogeneous if the distribution of the stereometric parameters is constant in a representative volume which is large compared with the size of the single particles. This means, that a quasihomogeneous material having a resulting conductivity will behave in a (electric-, temperature-) field in the same way as a homogeneous material of the same conductivity. The following will deal only with the conductivity of quasihomogeneous composites.

2) The theory of the conductivity of quasihomogeneous composites

2.1 The type of structure

It is known that particles of two phases can be arranged in two types of structures called the dispersion type (fig.3) and the structure of interconnecting phases (fig.4). The mentioned (equ.2) general equation will therefore separate in two functions:

$$(4a) \quad \lambda = f_1(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots)$$

$$(4b) \quad \lambda = f_2(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots)$$

2.2 The shape factor F

To have a measure for the shape of the (irregular) particles it is necessary to assume them by the most general regular body, for which the above mentioned perturbations in an original homogeneous field can be calculated. It is known that this regular shape can be only the ellipsoid of revolution. The perturbations are known as "Entelektrisierung", their magnitude being a function of the axial ratio main axis/subordinate axis, if the orientation of the main axis to direction of the field is constant. The axial ratio is always >1 for prolate, <1 for oblate spheroids and equal to 1 for spheres. Fig.5 shows the dependance of F on the axial ratio.

2.3 The orientation

The orientation is defined by the square of the cosine of the angles α between the axis of the ellipsoid (fig.6) and the direction of the original field: $\cos^2 \alpha_a, \cos^2 \alpha_b, \cos^2 \alpha_c$, with

$$(5) \quad \sum \cos^2 \alpha = 1$$

one gets for $b=c$ (spheroid)

$$(6) \quad \cos^2 \alpha_b + \cos^2 \alpha_c = 1 - \cos^2 \alpha_a = 1 - \cos^2 \alpha$$

α being the angle between the axis of revolution and the direction of the field.

2.4 The general equations for the resulting conductivity of composites

Based on /3/ there results the equation of the dispersion type of structure

$$(7) \quad 1 - C_D = \left(\lambda_M / \lambda \right)^m \cdot \frac{\lambda_D - \lambda}{\lambda_D - \lambda_M} \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda + n \lambda_D}{\lambda_M + n \lambda_D} \right)^P \quad /4/$$

$$m = \frac{F(1-2F)}{1 - \cos^2 \alpha (1-F) - 2F(1 - \cos^2 \alpha)}$$

$$n = \frac{1 - \omega \cos^2 \alpha (1 - F) - 2F(1 - \omega \cos^2 \alpha)}{2F(1 - \omega \cos^2 \alpha) + \omega \cos^2 \alpha (1 - F)}$$

$$\rho = \frac{F(1 - 2F)}{1 - \omega \cos^2 \alpha (1 - F) - 2F(1 - \omega \cos^2 \alpha)} + \frac{(1 - F)2F}{2F(1 - \omega \cos^2 \alpha) + \omega \cos^2 \alpha (1 - F)} - 1$$

$\lambda_{M,D}$ = conductivity of matrix and dispersed phase

c_D = Volume concentration of dispersed phase.

Special cases with typical values of shape and orientation are given in table (1). It is important to say, that equ.6 includes with $c_D = 0; 1$ the homogeneous, one-phase material and with $F = 0; 1/2$ and $\cos^2 \alpha = 0; 1$ the heterogeneous composite with parallel and series arrangement of the phases.

The general equation for the type of interconnecting phases /3/ is characterised by the fact that only the shape factor of $F = 1/2$ (infinitely long cylinder) is physically justified /4/. Then one gets

$$(8) (1 - c_{v1})(\lambda_2 - \lambda) \left[\frac{2(1 - \cos^2 \alpha)}{\lambda_2 + \lambda} + \frac{\cos^2 \alpha}{\lambda} \right] = \quad /4/$$

$$- c_{v1} (\lambda_1 - \lambda) \left[\frac{2(1 - \cos^2 \alpha)}{\lambda_1 + \lambda} + \frac{\cos^2 \alpha}{\lambda} \right]$$

3. Analysis of the microstructure of a composite

The application of equ. 7 and 8 needs an analysis and mathematical description of the microstructure of a real composite. The first thing necessary, is to state whether the composite is heterogeneous or quasihomogeneous. From fig.1 it is clear that an abrupt change of the shape and orientation of the particles of the phases is highly improbable, while this is possible for the concentration. Using an electronic image analyser the measurement of the concentration C_F in two planes perpendicular to each other can show an abrupt change as well as a systematic shift of the concentration, due to fabrication processes. In this case the sample has to be sub-

divided into regions, for which the concept of the quasihomogeneity is allowed. The whole sample then becomes a series-or-parallel arrangement of these phase regions, because a deviation from statistical distribution is probable only if during the fabrication process forces act in a particular direction. For this arrangement the two extreme cases for the conductivity are given in table 1.

3.1 Determination of the type of structure

The mathematical distinction between the both types of structure shown in fig.3 and 4 is a statistical problem. The answer was given in /5/, by calculating the probability of the formation of infinitely long chains W by single particles of the phases.

$$(9) \quad 1 - W = e^{-\bar{k} W} \quad /5/$$

where \bar{k} is the mean number of direct descendants for one particle in the chain. Values $W > 0.5$ indicate the presence of interconnecting phases.

$$(10) \quad 2\bar{m}_v = (\bar{k} + 1) [1 - f(0)] \quad /5/$$

The quantity \bar{k} is related to the mean number of contacts $2\bar{m}_v$ per particle and the fraction of particles without contacts to particles of the same phase $f(0)$. Equ. (9) and (10) are valid in volume. In /5/ the measurements of these two quantities from plane sections is given for the case that in the section plane the original particles in the chain are distinguishable. This is not the normal case. Taking the microstructure given in fig.4 it is obvious that another method has to be developed. This is described in detail in /6/. It is based on the fact that in a plane section of a microstructure three different features will appear (fig.7).

1. Nearly symmetrical sections of parts of the phase, which are taken as single particles,
2. linear chains without branches,
3. chains with one or more branches, which are divided in separate chains with i -branching points.

By measuring the mean diameter of the "single" particles per line and per area \bar{d}_L, \bar{d}_F and counting them (N_{eL}, N_{Fe}), measuring the mean length (\bar{l}_L, \bar{l}_F) and width (\bar{b}_L, \bar{b}_F) of the chains and counting the number of chains (k_L, k_F) and of the branching points i per area, the mean number of contacts per particle is given by:

$$(11) \quad 2\bar{m}_v = \frac{16}{\pi^2} \frac{M_F^2}{N_F^2} \bigg/ \frac{M_L}{N_L} \quad |7|$$

where

$$(12) \quad M_F = k_F \left[\frac{\bar{b}_F}{d_F} \left(\frac{\bar{c}_F}{d_F} - 1 \right) + \frac{\bar{c}_F}{d_F} \left(\frac{\bar{b}_F}{d_F} - 1 \right) \right] + i \frac{\bar{b}_F}{d_F} \quad |6|$$

which is the total number of contacts measured in the section plane.

The number of the original particles in the section plane is given by:

$$(13) \quad N_F = N_{Fe} + k_F \frac{\bar{c}_F \cdot \bar{b}_F}{d_F^2} \quad |6|$$

Analogie in linear analysis:

$$(14) \quad M_L = k_L \left(\frac{\bar{c}_L}{d_L} - 1 \right)$$

$$(15) \quad N_L = N_{Le} + k_L \frac{\bar{c}_L}{d_L} \quad |6|$$

The volume fraction of particles without contacts is given by:

$$(16) \quad f(0) = e^{-2\bar{m}_v}$$

The method was proved on a system bronze spheres-copper where the exact method of counting the contacts was possible. Table 2 gives the comparison and shows that the described method can be used for the determination of the type of structure.

3.2. The shape factor F.

It was already said, that the shape factor for the structure type of interconnecting phases must by $F = 1/2$, so the problem is to determine F for the dispersion structure. This can be done as follows. An irregular (threedimensional particle) shows in plane an irregular section which is approximated by an ellipse. The axial ratio b'/a' ,

b'-minor a'-major axis is determined by defining the maximum length of the irregular section as a', measuring the area (fig. 8) as:

$$(17) \quad A = \frac{\sqrt{L}}{4} a'b'$$

one gets the ratio for a single section of the irregular particle. The mean value of this ratio \bar{q}' (with respect to all possible section planes) can now be related to the axial ratio q (minor axis/major axis) of the spheroid [8]. The functions are shown in fig.9 separately for oblate and prolate spheroids. Here an additional problem arises. Only by measuring the mean axial ratio \bar{q}' in the plane it is not possible to decide whether the particles are prolate or oblate. The general case will be that in a powder fraction oblates and prolates with different axial ratios will exist so that in practice we shall have a distribution of axial ratios. To define the shape factor, we use however only the mean axial ratio for each type of spheroids \bar{q}_p, \bar{q}_o ; so that there results a mean shape factor \bar{F} :

$$(18) \quad \bar{F} = \frac{N_p}{N_v} F(\bar{q}_p) + \frac{N_o}{N_v} F(\bar{q}_o) \quad [8]$$

where N_p, N_o are the number of prolates and oblates per volume and N_v the total number of dispersed particles per volume. The procedure of getting the values \bar{q}_p, \bar{q}_o and the fraction of prolates or oblates respectively is given in detail in [4,8]. It was proved first on a model microstructure and then applied on a UO_2 -Cu cermet with UO_2 -spheres and UO_2 -particles of irregular shape [4]. The microstructure is shown in fig.10,11. The mean shape factor of these two samples are 0.33 for the UO_2 -spheres and 0.35 for the irregular particles. This should result in an nearly equal conductivity. The measured values of electrical conductivity for the both samples ($C_{UO_2} = 0,2$) were $3,59 \cdot 10^5 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $3,54 \cdot 10^5 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

3.3 The determination of the orientation

For a single prolate the orientation with respect to the normal of

the plane A in fig.12 is given by $\cos^2 \alpha_p$, if the shown spheroid would be an oblate its orientation with respect to the same plane would be $\cos^2 \alpha_0 = \cos^2(90 - \alpha_p)$. These values can now be related to the axial ratios q and q' in the following way:

$$(19) \quad \cos^2 \alpha_p = \frac{(b'/a')^2 \rho - q_p^2}{1 - q_p^2} \quad /4,8/$$

$$(20) \quad \cos^2 \alpha_0 = \frac{1 - q_0^2 (a'/b')_0^2}{1 - q_0^2} \quad /4,8/$$

Having a fully oriented dispersion type of structure only two orientations can appear bearing in mind, that in the composite prolates and oblates are present, than a mean orientation has to be defined

$$(21) \quad \overline{\cos^2 \alpha} = \frac{N_p}{N_v} \cos^2 \alpha_p + \frac{N_0}{N_v} \cos^2 \alpha_0 \quad /4,8/$$

For the case that the orientation of the particles will be random this (measured) value have to approach $\cos^2 \alpha = 1/3$, because for prolates as well as for oblates, the integral

$$(22) \quad \overline{\cos^2 \alpha} = \int_0^{\pi/2} \cos^2 \alpha \sin \alpha \, d\alpha = 1/3$$

which is the mean value for all possible orientations and is the value for statistic orientation. The orientation for the structure of inter connecting phases is given by equ.19, with $F=1/2; q_p=0$.

4. Experimental evidence in support of the theory

A satisfying comparison between experimental data and theory for the electrical conductivity and dielectric constant is given /19,18/

For the thermal conductivity this is done in the following way, measured values of the thermal conductivity of composites with known microstructure are compared with values calculated by theory.

Taking into account a mean uncertainty of $\pm 5\%$ for measured data of the thermal conductivity, and for the influence of uncertainties in determining the microstructure a margin of error of about $\pm 5\%$, the agreement between measured and calculated values is satisfying if the deviation is about $\pm 10\%$. Fig. 13,14 shows the concentration

function of λ in the systems U_3O_8 -Al and La_2O_3 -W /4/ over the whole concentration range. In the first, Al was dispersed in an U_3O_8 -powder matrix for all concentrations, while in the system La_2O_3 -W the structure type changes from W-matrix at 20 Vol.% La_2O_3 to interconnecting phase structure for 40, 60, 80 Vol.% La_2O_3 . In the system U_3O_8 -Al the Al-particles are near spherical /4/ so that an shape factor of 0,33 and statistical orientation ($\cos^2 \alpha$ 1/3) follows. Table 3 shows the comparison for several systems with interconnecting phase structure. Because of the implicitness of the equations 7,8 with respect to λ , the concentrations were calculated ($C_{cal.}$) using the equations and the measured thermal conductivities of the composite. These values are compared with the nominal ($C_{nom.}$) concentrations given in the literature. Table 4-7 shows the comparison for systems with dispersion type of structure. In these tables various values for the shape and orientation factor are realized. Taking in mind the above mentioned possible error the agreement between theory and experiment is satisfying for the predominant part of data referred.

5. The special case of porous materials

Equations describing the influence of porosity on the thermal conductivity are numerous. They are empirical or semi-empirical in that they are developed for a special kind of microstructure (for example /23/) and applied on samples with unknown microstructure.

Porosity in materials normally arises by the fabrication process, especially by sintering. Sintered samples however show two distinct ranges of porosities, the one zero to about 10% porosity, the second of 10% and higher. This is true for ceramics /22,24/ and for metals /25/. The range of low porosities is characterised by spherical pores owing to sintering mechanisms in the last stage of sintering. From this the porosity correction of the thermal conductivity in that range follows quite naturally from equ.7, setting $\lambda_D = 0$ and $F = 1/3$; $\cos^2 \alpha = 1/3$ the shape and orientation for spheres. Then one gets:

$$(23) \quad \lambda_p = \lambda_0 (1 - P)^{3/2} \quad P - \text{Porosity} \quad /20/$$

$\lambda_{p,0}$ - thermal conductivity (porous and dense material). The range of porosities higher than 10% (open porosity) is described by equation 8 with setting the thermal conductivity of one phase to zero

$$(24) (1-P)(\lambda_0 - \lambda_p) \left[\frac{2(1-\cos^2\alpha)}{\lambda_0 + \lambda_0} + \frac{\cos^2\alpha}{\lambda_p} \right] = P(2-\cos^2\alpha) \quad |4|$$

The examples of the comparison between theory and experiment given in fig.15-17 show that the equations 23,24 can be applied to porous materials. The amount of open porosities in the sample was determined by measuring the porosity of the sample with a high wetting fluid (Alumina fig.15, II, UN fig.17 /22/). The type of microstructure in the Alumina samples in fig. 15, I and 16 was given in the literature.

6. Comments on the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity of composites

The concept of an quasihomogeneous material as defined in the introduction does not take into account any kind of transport mechanisms for the thermal conductivity. It is a rigid application of field theory to the behaviour of materials in a field. The equ.7 and 8 include the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity of the composite by the temperature dependence of the conductivity of the pure phases. This means that interactions of transport mechanism does not take place. This should be true as long as the mean free path of the heat conductors is small compared with the size of the particles. In this sense the size, not mentioned as a stereometric parameter in this paper limits the application of the concept of quasihomogeneity to the thermal conductivity of composites.

Literature

- /1/ G. Ondracek, B. Schulz, Ber.DKG 48 (1971) 427
- /2/ G. Ondracek, B.Schulz, *ibid* 525
- /3/ W. Niesel, Ann.Phys.6 Folge 10 (1952) 336

- /4/ B. Schulz, KFK-1988 (1974)
- /5/ J. Gurland, 4.Planseeseminar, Reutte Tirol (1162) 507
- /6/ B. Schulz in: "Newsletter of Stereology 1974" KFK-Ext.6/74-4
- /7/ J. Gurland, Trans. AIME H8 (1958) 452
- /8/ G. Ondracek, B. Schulz, Prakt.Met.10 (1973) 2
- /9/ G. Ondracek, B. Schulz, *ibid* 10 (1973) 67
- /10/ U. Stille, Arch.Elektrotech.38 (1974) 91
- /11/ GEMP 1966, Rep. 55A, 59A, 400A (1967)
- /12/ J.D. Thomburg, C.D. Pears, ASME Paper 65-Wa/HT-4 (1965)
- /13/ E.O. Speidel u.a., BMI 1598 (1962)
- /14/ P. Weimar, Diss.Univers.Karlsruhe 1970
- /15/ Y.S. Toulikian, Thermophys.Prop.High Temp.Sol.Mat.Mc Millan N.Y. 1967
- /16/ L.N. Grossmann, NASA-CR-1154 (1968)
- /17/ B. Francois, J.P. Stora, J.Nucl.Mat.29 (1969) 302
- /18/ S. Nazarè, G. Ondracek, F. Thümmeler, KFK-1236 (1970)
- /19/ G. Ondracek, Werkstofftechnik H8 (1974)
- /20/ G. Ondracek, B. Schulz, J.Nucl.Mat.46 (1973) 253
- /21/ W.D. Kingery, J.L. Francl, J. Amer.Cer.Soc.37 (1954) 99
- /22/ T.Kikuchi, T.Takahashi, S. Nasu, J.Nucl.Mat.45 (1972/73)284
- /23/ A.L. Loeb, J.Amer.Cer.Soc.37 (1954) 96
- /24/ B. Schulz, to be published
- /25/ J.S. Hirschhorn, Introduction to Powder Metallurgy American Powder Metallurgy Institute N.Y. 1969

$\cos^2 \alpha$	Shape Factor F		
	0 (lamellae)	1/3 (Sphere)	1/2 (infinite long cylinder)
0 main axis of spheroid ⊥ to field	$1 - C_D = \frac{\lambda_D - \lambda}{\lambda_D - \lambda_M}$ a) (parallel array)		$1 - C_D = \frac{\lambda_D - \lambda}{\lambda_D - \lambda_M} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_M}{\lambda}}$ e)
1/3 main axis statisti- cal oriented	$1 - C_D = \frac{\lambda_D - \lambda}{\lambda_D - \lambda_M} \left(\frac{\lambda + 2\lambda_D}{\lambda_M + 2\lambda_D} \right)^{-1}$ b)	$1 - C_D = \frac{\lambda_D - \lambda}{\lambda_D - \lambda_M} \sqrt[3]{\frac{\lambda_M}{\lambda}}$ d)	$1 - C_D = \frac{\lambda_D - \lambda}{\lambda_D - \lambda_M} \left(\frac{5\lambda + \lambda_D}{5\lambda_M + \lambda_D} \right)^{-\frac{2}{5}}$ f)
1 main axis field	$1 - C_D = \frac{\lambda_D - \lambda}{\lambda_D - \lambda_M} \frac{\lambda_M}{\lambda}$ c) (series array)		$1 - C_D = \frac{\lambda_D - \lambda}{\lambda_D - \lambda_M}$ g) (parallel array)

Tab. 1: Special cases of equ.7 for the resulting conductivity of composites λ

Tab. 2: Probabilities W of formation of infinitely long chains in the system Bronze (Spheres) -Copper. Comparison between two methods (I, II) of evaluating W

Vol.% Bronze	W	
	I	II
20	0	0
30	0	0
40	0,06	0,18
50	0,75	0,59
60	0,95	0,90
70	>0,99	0,98

Tab. 3: Comparison of nominal and calculated concentrations in systems with structure type of interconnecting phases (equ.8) /4/

System	T[°C]	F	$\cos^2 \alpha$	c_{nom} [Vol%]	c_{cal} [Vol%]
Ag-Al ₂ O ₃	94,5	0,5	1/3	83 Al ₂ O ₃	87 Al ₂ O ₃
UO ₂ -W /11/	800	0,5	"	40 W	43 W
	1200	"	"	"	45 "
	1600	"	"	"	46 "
	800	"	"	60 W	64 "
	1200	"	"	"	64 "
	1600	"	"	"	63 "
Glass- fibers in polymers /12/	RT	"	0	22 Glass	17 Glass
	"	"	"	42 "	41 "
	"	"	"	53 "	55 "
	"	"	"	60 "	72 "
Graphite/ in polymers /12/	"	"	"	47 Graph.	45 Graph.
	"	"	"	57 "	55 "
	"	"	"	64 "	59 "
	"	"	"	71 "	65 "
UO ₂ -Mo /13/	100	"	1/3	60 UO ₂	53 UO ₂
	500	"	"	"	59 "
	900	"	"	"	63 "
UC-Mo /13/	100	"	"	60 UC	62 UC
	500	"	"	"	61 UC
	900	"	"	"	65 "

Tab. 4: Comparison of nominal and calculated concentrations in composites with metal matrix (equ.7 d in table 1) /4/

System	T[°C]	F	$\cos^2 \alpha$	c_{nom} [Vol%]	c_{cal} [Vol%]
UO ₂ -W /13/	100	1/3	1/3	50 Wolfram	45 Wolfram
	300	"	"	"	48 "
	500	"	"	"	49 "
	700	"	"	"	51 "
	900	"	"	"	53 "
	100	"	"	20 "	25 "
	300	"	"	"	26 "
	500	"	"	"	26 "
	700	"	"	"	26 "
	900	"	"	"	27 "
UO ₂ -Mo /14/	100	"	"	12 Molybdän	14 Molybdän
	"	"	"	20 "	17 "
	"	"	"	30 "	23 "
UO ₂ -Cr /14/	"	"	"	6 Chrom	6 Chrom
	"	"	"	12 "	13 "
	"	"	"	20 "	19 "
	"	"	"	30 "	27 "
UO ₂ -Nb /15/	400	"	"	80 UO ₂	82,5 UO ₂
	600	"	"	"	81 "
	800	"	"	"	72 "
	1000	"	"	"	70 "

Tab. 5: Comparison of measured and calculated thermal conductivities of composites with Me-Matrix (equ.7 d) /4/

System	T[°C]	F	$\cos^2 \alpha$	c[Vol%]	λ_{meas}	λ_{cal} [W/cmgrd]
UO ₂ -W /16/	1000	1/3	1/3	80 UO ₂	0,1	0,112
	1200	"	"	"	0,12	0,12
	1400	"	"	"	0,14	0,13
	1000	"	"	60 UO ₂	0,17	0,206
	1200	"	"	"	0,215	0,215
	1400	"	"	"	0,27	0,27

Tab. 6: Comparison of measured and calculated thermal conductivities in the system Bronze-Bakelit (equ.7) Bakelit-matrix /4/

System	T[°C]	F	$\cos^2 \alpha$	c[Vol%]	λ_{meas}	λ_{cal} [W/cmgrd]
Bronze-Bakelit	94,5	1/3	1/3	39 Bronze	0,004	0,0035
"	"	0,178	1	"	0,0022	0,0025
"	"	"	0	36 "	0,0053	0,0040

Tab. 7: Comparison of nominal and calculated concentrations in systems with metal-matrix, (equ.7) /4/

System	T[K]	F	$\cos^2 \alpha$	c_{cal} [metal]	c_{nom}
				Vol%	Vol%
UO ₂ -W /17/	1300	0.394	1	8	12
				16	20
UO ₂ -Fe /17/	"	"	1	18,4	25,3
				31	36,7
UO ₂ -Ni /17/	"	0,425	1	18,3	23,6
				30,2	34,6

a

b

c

Fig. 1: Possibilities of building up an heterogeneous composite by abrupt changes in concentration (a), shape (b), orientation (c)

Fig.2: Example of a quasi-homogeneous composite

Fig.3: The dispersion type of structure

Fig.4: The type structure of interconnecting phases

Fig. 5: Shape factor F as function of the axial ratio main/-subordinate axis. Curve after values from /10/

Fig.: 6: Definition of the orientation angle with respect to cartesian coordinates

Fig. 7: Main features of a Microstructure

Fig. 8: Plane sections of real particles and their approximation by Ellipses

Fig. 9: Mean value of axial ratio of ellipses as function of the axial ratio of the spheroid

Fig.10: Microstructure of an UO_2 -Cu-composite (200x); spherical UO_2

Fig.11: Microstructure of an UO_2 -Cu-composite (200x); irregular UO_2

Fig.12: Section through a spheroid with ellipse. $\alpha = \alpha_p$ orientation angle of P the main axis of the prolate with respect to the normal of plane A, section plane. $\alpha' = \alpha_o = 90 - \alpha_p$ orientation of the main axis of the oblate with respect to the plane A

Fig.13: Measured (•) and calculated (curve) thermal conductivity in the system U_3O_8 -Al /4/ $T=100^\circ C$

Fig.14: Measured (x) and calculated thermal conductivities in the system La_2O_3 -W T=1000°C /4/

Fig.15: Temperature functions of the thermal conductivity of porous Alumina
 · measured /21/ — calculated
 x this work
 I spherical pores 30% equ.23
 II open porosity 29% equ.24 $\cos^2 \alpha = 1/3$
 ($\lambda_0 = \lambda_{A_2O_3}$ 95% T.D. Standard)

Fig.16: Calculated (curves) and measured /21/
 thermal conductivities of porous Alumina
 I spherical pores (200°C) equ.23
 II Cylindrical pores (200°C)
 III Cylindrical pores (500°C)₂
 II, III pores heat flow; $\cos^2 \alpha = 1$
 equ.7, table 1, $\lambda_D = 0$

Fig.17: Calculated (curves) and measured thermal conductivities of porous UN /22/ equ.24;
 $\cos^2 \alpha = 1/3$